

Irooooo14 – Itserr

ReTINA₄Hortus

Document reference: ITSERR-10.5-[ReTINA₄Hortus]
Version number: 01.00
Status: FINAL
Last revision date: 27/03/2026 by: Andrea D'Andrea, Gilda Ferrandino
Verification date: 28/04/2026 by: Luisa Sernicola
Approval date: DD/MM/YYYY by: MUR
Subject: IRooooo14 – ITSERR
ReTINA₄Hortus
Filename: ITSERR_10.5_01.00_FINAL.docx

This document is available in the ITSERR WP Management document repository at:
ITSERR-WP10\05_Deliverables\D10.5_ReTINA₄Hortus

Change history

Version Number	Date	Status	Summary of main or important changes
00.01	27/03/2026	WORKING	Working version
00.02	27/04/2026	DRAFT	Complete revision of the document after ITSERR Board review
01.00	29/04/2026	FINAL	Finalisation

Distribution List

Name	Company	Role
ITSERR Board Members	All ITSERR partners	

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1 Document overview

1.1 Objectives

This deliverable aims at documenting the publication of ReTINA outputs — including source code, technical documentation, and structured metadata — in the RESILIENCE RI marketplace as open-source resources, in compliance with the guidelines presented in previous deliverables. ReTINA is a component of RESILIENCE RI designed to produce two main outputs. Firstly, it optimizes guidelines for the digitization and digital archiving of datasets of religious content from sites in the ancient world along the Nile Valley and its surroundings, including various languages and cultures. Secondly, building on these guidelines it produces a prototype software tool supporting scholars in the research and interpretation of this corpus. It has been packaged as open-source resources and published alongside technical documentation, source code, binaries, and structured metadata, in compliance with the guidelines established in previous project deliverables. All of those are published in Hortus platform. The ITSERR HORTUS is an integrated digital platform designed to support researchers in religious studies by providing seamless access to IT services, digital resources, and computational tools. It functions as a centralized repository where researchers can discover, access, and manage academic content, software, AI models, and collaborative tools. ITSERR supports research in Religious Studies by providing a secure, scalable, and FAIR-compliant digital environment. One of the key components of ITSERR is HORTUS, which serves as a centralized digital repository for research data, software tools, and IT services.

1.2 Scope

The main goal of the publication is to make ReTINA's blueprint and prototype software tool openly accessible to the academic community and research infrastructures, enabling students and scholars to adopt, reuse, and build upon the digitization guidelines and tools developed for the study of the Nile Valley ancient text corpus. By publishing these outputs in the marketplace, the WP10 aims to foster adoption, interoperability and reuse.

The users include researchers and institutions engaged in the study of the Nile Valley textual corpus and in the study of religious concept in the ancient world; digital archivists and developers seeking to extend or integrate the dataset and the prototype tool for annotation. The open access licensing model ensures that the outputs remain freely available, modifiable and redistributable, in accordance with the FAIR principles.

2 Published Output

2.1 Data Model and Digitization Guidelines

The guidelines developed throughout the project for the digitisation and digital archiving of Nile Valley and beyond corpora are published as open access deliverables and are intended to serve as guides for institutions and projects working with similar collections. The guidelines are released as PDF under a CC BY 4.0 license and can be consulted at the following webpage:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/itserr/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>.

They are also accessible via the Hortus Platform within the ReTINA project at the following webpage: <https://hortus-itserr.d4science.org/en/projects/project/e7f409f1-81ca-47bb-a9da-da7252e6a392>

Deliverable	Title	DOI
D10.1	White paper: Report on Digital Archives on Ancient Religious Content (DARCAR)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15025213
D10.2	Preliminary Data-Model	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15263295
D10.3	Data-Acquisition Procedures	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18508684
D10.4	Prototype for Annotation Tools and Interactive Interface (PRATI)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19347281

2.2 Dataset

The datasets are characterized by archaeological and museum objects related to Ethiopic manuscripts (12 manuscripts), magic Islamic bowls (100 items), amulets and personal ornaments of the Kerma Culture (Sudan) (97 items) and ritual religious artefacts from Seglamen (Ethiopia) (7 items). Objects are described as a resource in the Hortus marketplace. The resource contains descriptive metadata (xml) and documents such as photos (png, jpg), catalogue records (pdf), excavation documentation (pdf), 3D models (obj compressed in zip file), video. Metadata and documents are published in Open Access.

The datasets are published on the Hortus Platform under the ReTINA project, organized into four sub-projects: Ethiopic Manuscripts, The Amulets of Kerma Culture, The Aron Collection, and Ritual Religious Artefacts from Seglamen. All resources are released under a CC BY NC 4.0 license and are accessible at:

<https://hortus-itserr.d4science.org/en/projects/detail/e7f409f1-81ca-47bb-a9da-da7252e6a392>

2.3 Metadata

Metadata fields comply with the marketplace schema and with FAIR data principles. The primary metadata are based on Dublin Core.

Title	Title of the resource
Creation date	The date of the creation of the resource
Language	The language of documents and metadata
Rights	License
Type	It refers to the object
Subject	It refers to the object
Contributor	Institution
Published	Institution
Identifier	ID of the physical object
Description	Referred to the object

In addition, other metadata, referred to as "personnel," are created to describe the resources. Specific "personnel" metadata have been created for each subproject. According to the guidelines all of them describe the physical object, the writing text, the symbolic aspect and the archaeological context.

2.4 Prototypes

Two different prototypes have been developed to support users in use and reuse data. TEI2DC and Image Annotation Tool are specialized web application designed for digital archives and libraries. Both prototypes aimed at scholars, archivists, and researchers who need to analyse digital images from global libraries and museums by creating metadata layers over visual artifacts.

2.4.1 TEI2DC

Tool Name: TEI2DC
Version: 3.0
Programming Language: JavaScript
License: Open
Source Code Repository: HORTUS

TEI2DC is a specialized web application designed for digital archives and libraries. It is used to transform complex documents (in TEI/XML format) into standardized and "enriched" data

ready for the web (in RDF/XML format). It is a "Single Page Application" that runs entirely in the browser without requiring any installation. It is designed to convert metadata from manuscripts or ancient books into a format that international search engines and databases can easily read.

Languages Used:

- **HTML5 and CSS3:** Used for the structure and the dark mode interface, optimized to reduce eye strain during document study.
- **JavaScript:** Handles all the conversion logic, file loading, and interactivity.
- **XML/XSLT:** The "data languages" used by the app to transform texts from one format to another.

The interface is divided into three logical sections that guide the user through the workflow:

- **Image Viewer (IIIF):** Allows you to paste a link or drag and drop a digital scan of a document. You can zoom in and study the original image while working on its data.
- **Text Management (TEI):** This is where you load the file containing the document's description. The app provides a color-coded preview of the code to help identify errors.
- **Transformation & Enrichment:**
 - **Generation:** With a single click, the app extracts data (such as title, author, date) and converts it.
 - **Enrichment (Enrich):** The "smart" feature of the app; it searches for names of cities or institutions (e.g., "Naples") and automatically adds official links to international databases (like VIAF or GeoNames), making the data much more precise.
 - **Validation:** It checks that the result is correct and ensures no mandatory information is missing.

Once finished, the app allows you to download the final file ready for publication. It also generates a PDF report summarizing the work performed, including any errors or automatic corrections made.

2.4.2. Image Annotation Tool

Tool Name: Image Annotation Tool

Version: 2.0

Programming Language: JavaScript

License: Open

Source Code Repository: HORTUS

The application, titled Image Annotation Tool (V2.0) is a web-based platform designed to view high-resolution images via the IIIF protocol and allow users to create, manage, and export graphical and textual annotations. The main features are:

a. Viewing Capabilities

The app utilizes the OpenSeadragon library to provide a high-performance viewing experience:

- Loading IIIF Images: Users can load images directly from a IIIF endpoint URL.
- Local File Support: It supports uploading local images, local IIIF info.json manifests, or standard image files from the user's computer.
- Smooth Navigation: Users can zoom and pan across large images without performance lag.

b. Annotation Tools

The tool provides several ways to highlight specific areas of an image:

- Rectangle: For framing specific areas.
- Point: For marking precise coordinates with a pin.
- Freehand: For drawing custom paths using an SVG polyline that follows the mouse.
- Whole Image: For adding a general note or comment that applies to the entire file.

Each annotation includes a text area for entering notes or descriptions.

c. Metadata and State Management

The app includes a section for "Author" information to track:

- Author Name, Affiliation, and Date.
- Persistence: It uses the browser's localStorage to automatically save the work state (annotations and metadata), preventing data loss if the page is refreshed.

d. Import and Export

Designed for research and documentation, the app offers standardized export options:

- JSON-LD: Exports annotations using the W3C Web Annotation model.
- RDF/XML: An alternative XML-based format for data interoperability.
- Importing: Allows users to reload previously saved JSON-LD files to view or modify annotations on an image.

2.5 Training

WP10 has developed training materials that are published in HORTUS. Particularly, the HORTUS TC Training Centre, the Moodle-based platform, working as a huge library for all the training, where it is possible to find all the established categories of outputs to learn how to use the product developed by WP10.

The training material includes:

- Moodle courses
- Videos introducing the WP
- Video tutorial on the scientific outputs of WP10

2.5.1 Moodle Courses

The Moodle-based platform of ITSERR (ITSERR TC), integrated into HORTUS, is the training output of the ITSERR project intended for a broad academic and professional audience. Particularly, WP10 has developed for Moodle 1 course, dedicated to ReTINA, named "Custodire il Sacro: proposte di linee guida per la conservazione digitale degli oggetti magico-religiosi dalla Valle del Nilo e oltre. I dataset di RETINA.

The course dedicated to ReTINA is available on the HORTUS TC:

WP	TITLE OF THE MOODLE COURSE	Link to the Course on HORTUS Training centre
10	"Custodire il Sacro: proposte di linee guida per la conservazione digitale degli oggetti magico-religiosi dalla Valle del Nilo e oltre. I dataset di RETINA."	Corso: Custodire il Sacro: proposte di linee guida per la conservazione digitale degli oggetti magico-religiosi dalla Valle del Nilo e oltre. I dataset di RETINA Hortus Training Centre

A description of the Moodle course is available as follows:

Custodire il Sacro: proposte di linee guida per la conservazione digitale degli oggetti magico-religiosi dalla Valle del Nilo e oltre. I dataset di RETINA/ Preserving the Sacred: Proposed Guidelines for the Digital Preservation of Magical and Religious Objects from the Nile Valley and Beyond. The RETINA Datasets (Authors: Andrea D'Andrea, Gilda Ferrandino, Alexia Pavan, Tarik Ranieri – Università degli Studi di Napoli "l'Orientale")

The aim of the course is to outline guidelines for the digitization of magical-religious artefacts and texts from the Nile Valley and beyond. These materials are characterized by a

layering of ritual, symbolic and iconographic meanings that are difficult to document using traditional morphological and typological approaches. Their complexity stems from the interplay between text, image and material. Digitization therefore requires a flexible and semantically rich model, capable of expressing the relationships between the various components. The use of structured metadata and controlled vocabularies facilitates data sharing and interoperability, in accordance with the FAIR principles.

. The Moodle course also includes 1 video introducing the main features of the tool and 1 video tutorial dedicated to discover all the main functions of the tool and dataset.

The course is organized into 9 modules. The first module provides the conceptual and methodological foundations for documenting archaeological objects that present a particular challenge: they are carriers of deep sacred and cultural meanings yet often come to us with incomplete or entirely absent contextual information. The module essentially serves as a "preparatory course" that: clarifies WHY these objects differ from other artefacts; introduces the PROBLEMS related to the presence and absence of context; and presents the basic TOOLS to address these challenges.

The second module explains the rationale behind the digitization of cultural heritage objects. Digitizing cultural heritage involves creating digital copies of ancient objects using photographs, 3D models, and scientific analyses. This enables detailed study without physical handling, prevents damage, and allows global sharing. It also helps preserve fragile artefacts, enhance inscriptions, and even reconstruct lost items through digital means.

The third and fourth modules address data management and knowledge formalization, providing guidelines and practical suggestions for the description of ancient magical-religious texts using established standards for editing and research.

The fifth module introduces archaeometry and its role in the analysis and interpretation of cultural heritage materials.

Modules six through nine illustrate the datasets used as case studies. These modules present datasets from the Nile Valley and Southern Arabia, with reference to the RETINA project, which studies complex, rare, and/or endangered religious texts written on various media (stone, papyrus, etc.). The material covered is extremely heterogeneous in terms of culture, language, and historical period.

2.5.2 Video introducing the WP

Among the training materials for RESILIENCE produced by WP10 and also integrated into the courses available on the HORTUS Training Centre as learning resource of the ReTINA Moodle course, there is 1 video introducing the main themes addressed by WP10, contextualised within the broader objectives of ITSERR. The target audience consists of

students and researchers in the fields of archaeology, art history and philology with a basic understanding of the Semantic Web.

WP	TITLE OF THE VIDEO
10	<i>ReTINA</i>

2.5.3 Video-tutorials on scientific outputs of WP10

As part of the ITSERR project, 1 educational tutorial has been produced for WP10, dedicated to its scientific outputs and included in the Training Materials for RESILIENCE. The tutorial aims to present the features and capabilities of the datasets developed within the project. Also this educational tutorial produced by WP10 will be available as learning resource on the HORTUS TC.

WP	TITLE OF THE VIDEO
10	<i>ReTINA Dataset</i>

(End of Document)